

Newsletter 7 / 2020

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Events that ESIWACE will participate in or has participated in

- [Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather](#), online, 23-28 August, 2020
- [OASIS3-MCT online course](#), 6-10 July, 2020
- [ESiWACE2 Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling](#), online, 30 June, 2020
- [The HPC IO in the Data Center workshop](#), 25 June, 2020
- [6th ENES HPC Workshop](#), online, 25-26 & 28-29 May, 2020

News & updates

Virtual 6th ENES HPC Workshop and ESIWACE2 annual meeting

From 25 to 29 May, 2020, DKRZ hosted the 6th HPC workshop of the European Network for Earth System Modelling (ENES) as a virtual event within the framework of ESIWACE2. This year's event was the 6th one in a series of workshops organized by the "ENES HPC-Task Force" roughly every two years, and was held virtually for the first time. The workshop aimed at bringing together scientists from the fields of earth system modeling, informing them about the latest developments in high performance computing and fostering a mutual exchange among each other and with HPC experts.

The four workshop sessions on *very high-resolution modeling*, *performance portability*, *machine learning for parameterization schemes* and *challenges in exascale data processing and visualization* with a total of 35 talks were spread over four days and attracted about 180 participants in total: from 12 European countries, the United States, China, Japan and India.

On May, 27, the workshop was suspended for the ESIWACE2 annual meeting, which also was held as a videoconference. The annual meeting saw 53 attendees from ESIWACE2 consortium member institutions and in addition to progress reports from the seven work packages, this full day meeting comprised discussions on merging workflows, sustainability and HPC initiatives.

See also:

<https://www.esiwace.eu/results-1/showroom/virtual-6th-enes-hpc-workshop-and-esiwace2-annual-meeting>

Event page: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/6th-hpc-workshop>

ESiWACE2 Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling

On June 30, 2020, the Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling was held as a virtual event within the framework of ESIWACE2, the Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe. The workshop organized by Giovanni Aloisio (CMCC), Graham Riley (UNIMAN), Carlos Osuna (METEOSWISS) and Sandro Fiore (CMCC) was hosted by DKRZ with the local support of Dela Spickermann and Florian Ziemer under the

supervision of the ESIWACE2 Coordinator Joachim Biercamp. The workshop was funded by the Horizon 2020 project ESIWACE2.

Due to the situation with COVID-19, the event was held as a virtual conference with approximately 143 participants mainly from Europe and the US, but also from Brazil, India and Israel.

Scientists working in the fields of earth system modeling, machine learning, exascale hardware/computing, and programming models attended the workshop, receiving and exchanging information about the latest developments in those fields, also involving HPC experts.

The agenda of the workshop was organized in three sessions with a total of 17 talks focusing on *exascale hardware, programming models and hardware interplay, and machine learning*.

Despite being virtual, the workshop was successful in all the three sessions with a lot attendees and questions for speakers during the Q&A.

Link: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/virtual-ws-on-emerging-technologies/virtual-ws-on-emerging-technologies>

Seminar talk by Peter Dueben on machine learning for weather predictions

Peter Dueben of ECMWF has recently given a talk at the ML seminar of Oxford physics. In his talk he explained how machine learning (ML), and in particular deep learning, could help to improve weather predictions in the coming years. He also presented ongoing work related to machine learning at ECMWF. The recording of the talk is available on [YouTube](#) and slides can be accessed [here](#).

Snapshots

BSC

We have been working on the preparation of two new configurations for EC-Earth4 (medium and high resolution). For this EC-Earth version, we want to use a new tool (ocp-tool) to automate the generation of all the files needed for coupled runs.

We are also working on the preparation of the XIOS benchmark using OpenIFS and some large runs in Mare Nostrum 4 in August (before the annual electrical maintenance, we can use the machine for large allocations) as we did last year. We plan to run NEMO and OpenIFS-XIOS simulations.

Bull Atos

In the framework of the GENCI's Technology Watch Unit, the Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean (NEMO), used in large variety of applications (weather or climate forecast, global or regional focus, ...) has been analyzed on the Arm platform at the TGCC/CEA. For more information see [Arm's HPC blog post](#).

CERFACS

The first part of the OASIS3-MCT online course is completed and the first session was held on July 6-10 2020 with 10 participants from LEGOS (France) and the MetOffice (UK). We are looking forward to the feedback from those users on this first online experience with OASIS3-MCT!

CMCC

A first version of the ESDM PAV runtime is under development. This version is designed to support both post-processing (CDO) and data-analytics (Ophidia) operators. A Python API has been designed to programmatically support the ESDM PAV experiment schema. Moreover, an initial integration of the Ophidia framework with ESDM for I/O, by means of the esdm-netcdf library, has been completed. CMCC has been co-organizing the ESiWACE2 Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling, held on June 30, 2020.

DKRZ

We have organized and hosted the ESiWACE2 annual meeting on 27 May and the Virtual 6th ENES HPC workshop on 25-26 and 28-29 May, 2020, both of which took place as virtual meetings using video conference software. A short report on the workshop (D6.3) has been submitted to the EC and published on Zenodo. Additionally, we supported CMCC, UNIMAN and MeteoSwiss in organizing and hosting the ESiWACE2 Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling on June 30, 2020, which will feed into the white paper D2.6.

Together with MPI-M, we have successfully applied for compute time on the Mistral supercomputer and obtained an allocation of 256650 node hours and 329 TB of disk space for DYAMOND simulations and storage of output from the intercomparison project for the second half of 2020.

We are currently gathering contributions to and preparing the first ESiWACE2 periodic report to be submitted to the EC by end of August.

ECMWF

We have started to work on the DYAMOND winter case model configurations. In particular, we have been working to enable 3D ocean model output at the required output frequencies for the entire time period of 40 days.

ETH Zürich / CSCS

After the success of the Container Hackathon in December, we have had several requests from third parties for information about it. Fortunately, all the hackathon experiences are in the public domain and can be found at the event repository <https://github.com/eth-cscs/ContainerHackathon> or in the ESIWACE-2 D2.8 deliverable. Containers will also be a topic during one afternoon at the ESIWACE-2 summer school, mentioned in the Events section. ETH Zürich will be represented by Alberto Madonna, who will present about 2 hours of lecture material and will lead a lab exercise on Docker.

NLeSC

Together with ATOS-BULL the Netherlands eScience center is working on the projects granted in WP3 service 1, accelerating geoscientific codes of external groups in Europe. In short, we are exploring GPU-porting of the ocean model FESOM-2, we are improving the scalability of the atmospheric large-eddy simulator DALES, we are reducing the memory footprint of atmospheric chemistry on the GPU in the MESSy framework and finally parallelizing the ice-sheet atmosphere coupler OBLIMAP.

STFC (UKRI)

We presented PSyclone progress at the 6th ENES HPC workshop and progress on DSLs in ESIWACE2 at the ESIWACE2 Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling.

We have continued to improve support for the NEMO model in PSyclone and the performance of the Ocean part of the model is now slightly faster on a V100 GPU using PSyclone compared with a Skylake CPU running the original NEMO MPI code. Manual analysis of the current V100 performance has shown that with some additional PSyclone development, the V100 GPU performance of the Ocean part of the model will be approximately 2x the performance of a Skylake CPU. However, the sea-ice part of the model still requires significant improvement.

We have continued to improve support for the translation of a NEMO tracer advection benchmark from PSyclone's internal representation to the representation used by DAWN. In particular, the PSyclone front end has been extended to support declarations using the `"*n"` notation e.g. `REAL*8` and work is ongoing to support the translation of array notation (implicit loops) to explicit loops via a PSyclone transformation as the SIR does not support the concept of implicit loops.

Lastly we have started writing an independent learning PSyclone tutorial using Jupyter notebooks. This will be used as part of the Extreme Scale Computation session at the upcoming ESIWACE2 Summer School.

UniMan

We helped organise the ESIWACE2 Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling held on June 30th. We have drafted our contribution to the WP2 deliverable D2.4 based on our experiences with optimising a tracer advection example code on GPUs using OpenACC. The results are being used to inform PSyclone developers on optimisation techniques for such codes and they will form a component for the comparison of the DSL

approaches. We have also begun discussions with relevant partners on our upcoming optimisation work related to ESDM-PAV in work package 5.

University of Reading

The [Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather](#) is now a virtual event with a slightly modified agenda. Participants are welcome to attend this free event! Simply use the lightweight registration process. We are currently contributing skill definitions for IO to the [HPC Certification Forum](#).

Recent ESIWACE2-related Publications

BSC presented the poster “*May deep learning contribute to improve downscaling techniques?*” in the ISMS 2020 (International Symposium on Marine Sciences). BSC researcher Jesús Peña Izquierdo, in collaboration with Carlos Gómez and the Earth System Services team, has presented an initial work to use deep learning to improve downscaling.

May Deep Learning contribute to improve Downscaling techniques?

Summary

Downscaling techniques are a common data-driven methodology used to generate high-resolution forecasts without the need of running computationally expensive simulations. Climate models from low-resolution resolution are used to feed an algorithm which generates high-resolution forecasts. The accuracy of these forecasts is limited by the coarse resolution of the input data. In this work, we explore the use of deep learning to improve the accuracy of these forecasts. We focus on the downscaling of precipitation and temperature. In particular, we focus on the downscaling of precipitation. We use a deep learning model to improve the accuracy of the forecasts. The model is trained on a dataset of high-resolution precipitation and temperature data. The model is then used to generate high-resolution forecasts. The results show that the model is able to improve the accuracy of the forecasts.

Dataset

The dataset used in this work consists of high-resolution precipitation and temperature data. The data is obtained from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) reanalysis. The data is used to train the deep learning model. The model is then used to generate high-resolution forecasts. The results show that the model is able to improve the accuracy of the forecasts.

Model

The model used in this work is a deep learning model. The model is trained on a dataset of high-resolution precipitation and temperature data. The model is then used to generate high-resolution forecasts. The results show that the model is able to improve the accuracy of the forecasts.

Results

The results of the model are compared against the high-resolution data. The results show that the model is able to improve the accuracy of the forecasts. The model is able to generate high-resolution forecasts that are more accurate than the low-resolution data. The results show that the model is able to improve the accuracy of the forecasts.

Conclusions

The results of this work show that deep learning can be used to improve the accuracy of downscaling techniques. The model is able to generate high-resolution forecasts that are more accurate than the low-resolution data. The results show that the model is able to improve the accuracy of the forecasts.

Acknowledgements

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References

1. Peña Izquierdo, J., Gómez, C., & Escribano, J. (2020). May deep learning contribute to improve downscaling techniques? In *International Symposium on Marine Sciences (ISMS 2020)*. Barcelona, Spain: ISMS 2020.

A poster named “*ESIWACE HPC services for Weather and Climate models*” and the associated video, prepared by Erwan Raffin (Atos Bull), Ben van Werkhoven (NLeSC) and Florian Ziemann (DKRZ), have been presented at ISC 2020. It focuses on granted Service 1 projects for 2020 dealing with FESOM2, EMAC, DALES and OBLIMAP2 codes. An overview of each project is presented with the associated goals. Through this poster we encourage other groups developing and maintaining weather and climate codes to apply to next project calls.

[Link to the poster](#)

[Link to the video](#)

The project ESIWACE2 has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823988.

OVERVIEW

The Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe (ESIWACE) will push the global high-resolution demonstrators towards production-ready simulations on European pre-exascale and future exascale systems. ESIWACE2 further focuses on exploring and exploiting suitable innovative technologies such as design specific languages, on the development of processing tools for more efficient I/O and visualization and on providing enhanced services, training and benchmarks for the community.

ESIWACE2 offers and supports various training programmes on pre-exascale HPC software engineering, methods and tools for engineers and scientists in the domain of weather and climate. These trainings constitute a transfer of general knowledge from ESIWACE2 experts to the community.

Poster Focus: HPC user-services

Within the ESIWACE2 project, open HPC services to the Earth system modelling community in Europe are provided.

The goal of these services is to create collaborations that provide guidance, engineering, and advice to support exascale preparations for weather and climate models. It is aimed to improve model efficiency and to enable to port models to existing and upcoming European tier0 systems.

All groups developing and maintaining weather and climate codes - not only the ESIWACE2 partners - can apply. Proposals for such collaboration projects will be peer-reviewed and those found eligible will be granted in-kind support by one of the partners involved.

Three types of services are proposed:

- Service 1: Model portability and refactoring
- Service 2: Coupling, input, output and workflows
- Service 3: Weather and climate benchmarking

Focus on Service 1: Model portability and refactoring - Granted projects for 2020

FESOM2	EMAC	DALES	OBLIMAP2
Global sea-ice and ocean circulation model	ECMWF/MESV Atmospheric General Circulation Model (AGCM)	Dutch Atmospheric Large Eddy Simulation	Fast climate model-ice sheet model coupling
Profile FESOM2 with GPUs in mind, and port the best suited numerical kernels to GPUs	Improve performance and memory of current CUDA version of the code to GPUs	Improve overall performance	Resolve the memory bottleneck in the code with MPI shared memory
Get a fresh view on FESOM2 optimization in general	Extend its capability to be able to handle a wider range of magnitude more complex chemistry	Focus on thermodynamics code	Implementing parallel I/O
		Investigate use of single precision	Scale performance to multiple nodes

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